

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STIGMATIZATION OF PEOPLE WITH DEPRESSION AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS: LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Aim of the Study: This thesis aims to investigate the stigmatization of individuals with depression among medical students through an extensive literature review. It seeks to explore various dimensions of stigma, including its origins, manifestations, impact, and potential interventions. By systematically analyzing existing research, the study intends to contribute significantly to understanding and addressing the stigma surrounding depression within the medical student community.

Keywords: Stigma, Depression, Medical Students, Mental Health, Help-seeking Behavior, Education, Intervention, Well-being, Academic Performance.

Materials and Methods: A rigorous search was conducted across multiple databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, PsycINFO, Embase, and institutional libraries, focusing on stigma related to depression among medical students. Only articles published within the last decade were considered to ensure the inclusion of recent research. The data synthesis encompassed prevalence rates, contributing factors, manifestations of stigma, and potential interventions to combat stigma against individuals with depression among medical students.

Outcomes: The study underscores the detrimental effects of stigmatization of individuals with depression among medical students. It emphasizes that recognizing and addressing stigma are essential for promoting the well-being of both students and patients. Stigmatization can lead to reluctance in seeking help, exacerbation of symptoms, and compromised academic and professional performance among medical students. Effective interventions targeting stigma are crucial for fostering a supportive learning environment and enhancing mental health outcomes.

Clinical Manifestations and Implications: Stigmatization of individuals with depression among medical students manifests in various ways, including negative attitudes, stereotypes, and discriminatory behaviors. Beyond its immediate impact on affected individuals, stigma can perpetuate misconceptions about mental illness, hinder help-seeking behaviors, and contribute to a culture of silence surrounding mental health issues within the medical community. Addressing stigma is paramount for promoting empathy, understanding, and compassionate care among future healthcare professionals.

Diagnostic Approaches: The diagnostic process for stigma related to depression among medical students involves understanding the underlying beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors contributing to stigmatizing attitudes. Self-assessment tools, surveys, and qualitative interviews can aid in identifying the prevalence and manifestations of stigma within the medical student population. Recognizing the unique stressors and challenges faced by medical students is crucial for designing targeted interventions to combat stigma effectively.

Interventions and Strategies: Interventions to address stigma related to depression among medical students encompass educational initiatives, destigmatization campaigns, and promoting open discussions about mental health. Encouraging empathy, fostering resilience, and cultivating a supportive peer environment are vital components of effective stigma-reduction strategies. Moreover, integrating mental health education into medical curricula and providing access to confidential support services can facilitate a culture of acceptance and understanding within the medical education setting.

Conclusion: In conclusion, this abstract highlights the pervasive nature of stigma surrounding depression among medical students and its adverse effects on individuals' well-being and academic performance. By elucidating the origins, manifestations, and implications of stigma, this study aims to contribute to efforts aimed at destigmatizing depression within the medical student community. It emphasizes the importance of implementing targeted interventions and fostering a culture of empathy, acceptance, and support to address stigma effectively.

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